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**“Excellence hub in green technologies: Introducing innovation ecosystems in
the Mediterranean food value chain”**

EXCEL4MED

Co-Creation Workshop with relevant stakeholders to fill in the Business Model Canvas

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Abstract

This document presents a summary of the four Living Labs organised within the framework of the EXCEL4MED project, corresponding to Deliverable D2.3 “Co-Creation Workshop with relevant stakeholders to fill in the Business Model Canvas” and developed as part of Work Package 2. The Living Labs, held in Greece and Malta, brought together diverse stakeholders, including researchers, industry representatives, policymakers, local producers and consumers to collaboratively address sustainability challenges in Mediterranean food supply chains. The workshops employed structured methodologies such as the Q-methodology and the Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas, alongside a governance dimension, to explore solutions for waste valorisation, green technologies, innovative business models and sustainable practices. Key outcomes include actionable strategies to enhance transparency, operational efficiency and collaboration across the value chain, while addressing economic, environmental, and social dimensions. This deliverable underscores EXCEL4MED’s commitment to fostering resilience and innovation in Mediterranean food systems through multi-stakeholder collaboration and co-creation.

Executive Summary

This document has been developed as part of EXCEL4MED's Work Package 2 and presents the outcomes of **deliverable D2.3 "Co-Creation Workshop with relevant stakeholders to fill in the Business Model Canvas"**, as well as the EXCEL4MED efforts in **Task 2.4 "Map stakeholders" organisational models using a tailored Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas combined with a "Governance layer"**.

This document provides a detailed summary of the four Living Labs organised within the EXCEL4MED framework, and it offers an overview of each Living Lab, including general information, participant profiles, activities, agendas, methodologies applied, key discussions, findings and outcomes.

Additionally, it describes the dissemination and communication materials developed for each Living Lab, including promotional materials (such as videos, images...), social media posts, articles and press releases.

Following the introduction, this deliverable offers a comprehensive overview of the four Living Labs. It concludes with a summary of the key insights and outcomes, and includes annexes containing supporting materials, such as detailed agendas and the communication outputs developed during these activities.

1. Introduction

The EXCEL4MED project aims to foster sustainable innovation within Mediterranean food supply chains, focusing on enhancing resilience, sustainability and circularity. As part of its strategy to engage diverse stakeholders and collect key insights for the development of a Business Model Canvas, the project organised a series of Living Labs. These workshops serve as collaborative spaces where stakeholders, researchers and consumers can exchange ideas and shape the direction of the project's innovations. Each of the Living Labs focused on distinct aspects of the Mediterranean food system, such as sustainable business practices, green technologies and consumer expectations.

The **first EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta** (4-5 May 2023) was divided into two sessions: the first session brought together 39 stakeholders to explore green technologies and sustainability challenges, with discussions guided by Q-methodology. During the second session, held on the following day, 28 consumers participated to share their ideas on sustainable food practices. These workshops provided valuable input for refining the project's consumer survey. Meanwhile, during the **first EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece** (4 July 2023), 30 participants from agriculture, research and policy sectors, as well as consumers, gathered at the Agricultural University of Athens. This Living Lab focused on sustainable innovations in food processing, using Q-methodology to explore opportunities for greener business practices and cross-sector collaboration.

On the other hand, the **second EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece** (27 September 2024) gathered 22 participants from the Greek food and beverages sector. Discussions focused on innovative business models, green technologies and value-added product development for pomegranates and citrus fruits. The event applied the Business Model Canvas methodology, enabling stakeholders to align strategies with sustainability goals. Regarding the **second EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta** (21 November 2024) brought together 57 participants, including representatives from industry, government and academia, to address economic, environmental and social dimensions of sustainability. Using the Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas, the event facilitated workshops on waste valorisation, sustainable packaging and community-driven strategies to enhance the Mediterranean food supply chain.

These four Living Labs collectively provided practical insights, strengthened collaboration between Greece and Malta and laid the groundwork for advancing innovative, sustainable practices across Mediterranean food systems.

2. Overview of the four EXCEL4MED Living Labs

2.1 First EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta (4-5 May 2023)

Figure 1. EXCEL4MED partners in the first Living Lab in Malta (4-5 May 2023)

General information

The first EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta was held on **4-5 May 2023** at the **Malta Life Sciences Park (MLSP)**, located in **San Gwann (Malta)**.

This Living Lab consisted of two sessions, each focusing on distinct but complementary aspects of stakeholder and consumer engagement.

Key partners included the **MLSP** and **The Malta Chamber of Commerce (TMC)**, as the organisers of the event, alongside the EXCEL4MED partners the **International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM-IAMM)**, the Malta Food Agency (MFA), **Koperattivi Malta (KM)** and the **University of Malta (UM)**, who contributed as facilitators, organisers and presenters.

Participants

The first session of the 1st Living Lab in Malta, which took place on 4 May 2023, brought together **39 stakeholders** from various sectors, all contributing valuable insights to the discussions. Participants included representatives from public organisations, private

enterprises, cooperatives and NGOs, such as Atriga Consulting Services, Nature Trust - FEE Malta, EkoSkola Malta, Malta Crafts Foundation, Circular Economy Malta, Farmers Central Cooperative and the Malta Council for Science and Technology, among others.

Profiles of stakeholders

- **Public sector representatives:** senior officials and policy officers from organisations like Malta Enterprise, Malta Food Agency and the Malta Council for Science and Technology, including heads of departments and chief officers.
- **Private sector leaders:** CEOs, managing directors, and marketing professionals from businesses such as consulting firms, manufacturing companies and sustainability-oriented enterprises.
- **NGO representatives:** educators and environmental advocates from organisations like Nature Trust and Circular Economy Malta.
- **Academic and research institutions:** RD&I project assistants and other experts contributing to research and innovation.

The second session, held on 5 May 2023, focused on engaging consumers to gather their perspectives and preferences related to sustainable practices in the food industry. This session included **28 citizens/consumers** from various professional and personal backgrounds. The diversity in participant profiles enriched the discussions, leading to a well-rounded understanding of consumer expectations and their alignment with the project's goals for sustainability and innovation in Mediterranean food systems.

Profiles of consumers

- **Public and educational sector representatives:** retired educators and individuals with experience in teaching and public service contributed their community-based perspectives.
- **Private sector professionals:** directors, managers, and junior officers from businesses such as manufacturing firms, consultancy companies, and research organizations provided insights on consumer-facing trends and sustainability practices.
- **Financial sector contributors:** representatives from banking and business development roles offered perspectives on market dynamics and economic considerations.
- **Research and innovation experts:** senior research officers and project assistants shared their understanding of sustainable technologies and their potential applications in daily life.
- **Independent participants:** unaffiliated attendees provided unbiased consumer insights, ensuring the inclusion of perspectives from individuals not tied to specific organisations.

Activities and agenda

The first day began with an **internal project partner meeting**, where team members from various organisations, including **MLSP, CIHEAM-IAMM, TMC, MFA and KM**, came together to prepare for the **stakeholder workshop**.

Key activities kicked off with an **introduction and overview**, during which participants were welcomed and introduced to the **objectives of the workshop**. The main focus of the day was the **Innovation-Oriented Living Lab (T2.3)**, aimed at identifying **research and innovation (R&I) needs** to drive **sustainable business practices**.

During the workshop, **presentations** were delivered by **TMC** and **UoM**, where they provided an overview of the **EXCEL4MED project** and introduced **green technologies** proposed by **UoM**. These presentations set the stage for deeper discussions, guided by **facilitators from CIHEAM-IAMM** and other partner organisations, who led the group in exploring the identified R&I needs.

The day concluded with a **project partner meeting** to prepare for the second session, followed by a **networking dinner**, which provided an excellent opportunity to foster collaboration among the partners.

The second day shifted focus to **citizen engagement** and **consumer insights**, which were essential for informing the development of the **consumer survey**. The day began with an **introduction and overview**, during which **partners, stakeholders and citizens** were welcomed, and **TMC** and **UoM** introduced the **EXCEL4MED project** and the **Living Lab approach**. The core activity was the **consumer workshop**, where **facilitators from TMC, UoM and CIHEAM-IAMM** led discussions to better understand **consumer needs and preferences**. Topics covered included **product expectations** and **sustainability considerations**. During this session, a **collaborative effort** was made to refine the questions for the **consumer survey**, ensuring that they were closely aligned with the project's goals.

The day wrapped up with a **summary of outcomes** and the identification of the **next steps** for the project (for further information, see Figure 13).

Methodologies applied

One of the methodologies used was the **Q-methodology**, which combined qualitative and quantitative data to explore stakeholder perspectives on proposed green technologies. This approach enabled a deeper understanding of attitudes and informed the design of subsequent project activities.

In addition, the **interactive workshop format** provided a platform for both structured discussions and open dialogue with stakeholders and consumers/citizens.

Main discussions and findings

Stakeholder workshop (Day 1):

The first session brought stakeholders together to evaluate green technologies and their potential to enhance the Mediterranean agri-food sector. Participants delved into the research and innovation needs for sustainable business practices, identifying key barriers and opportunities that could shape the successful implementation of these technologies.

Central to the workshop was the use of **Q-methodology**, which allowed stakeholders to articulate their perspectives on sustainability and innovation. This approach fostered a rich exchange of diverse viewpoints, uncovering valuable insights into the challenges and potential pathways for integrating sustainable practices into the food industry.

Consumer workshop (Day 2):

The second session shifted focus to consumers, inviting them to share their thoughts, ideas and preferences regarding sustainable food practices. These discussions underscored the importance of making eco-friendly products accessible to a wider audience while maintaining transparency in food production processes.

Participants emphasised the value of local, high-quality products in fostering consumer trust and loyalty. They also explored how their individual behavior and choices could play a significant role in building a more sustainable food system. This collective dialogue highlighted the shared responsibility among producers and consumers in achieving a greener and more resilient Mediterranean food ecosystem.

Outcomes

Stakeholder workshop (Day 1):

The insights gathered during this session were instrumental in shaping strategies for integrating green technologies into Mediterranean food supply chains. The findings from the Q-methodology provided a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder priorities, which directly informed the planning of subsequent project activities. Additionally, participants identified key opportunities for collaboration among businesses, researchers and policymakers, which are essential for driving innovation within the sector.

Consumer workshop (Day 2):

The workshop provided valuable feedback on consumer expectations and behaviours, which will be crucial for designing sustainable food products. This input also played a significant role in refining the project's survey questionnaires, ensuring they are aligned with consumer

priorities. Furthermore, it highlighted the importance of promoting local, sustainable food products as a central element to achieving the project's overall objectives.

Dissemination and communication

- **Pre-event:** posts in the different social networks of the project (see Figure 15), and outreach materials (Figure 11) were shared to announce the Living Lab and invite participants.
- **Post-event:** posts in the different social networks of the project (Figure 15), as well as two articles for the EXCEL4MED website (Figure 14) were created to share the outcomes and amplify the event's impact.

Figure 2. Pictures from the first Living Lab in Malta (4-5 May 2023)

2.2 First EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece (4 July 2023)

Figure 3. First Living Lab in Greece (4 July 2023)

General information

The first Greek Living Lab of the EXCEL4MED project took place on **4 July 2023**, at the premises of the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA).

The event brought together a diverse group of stakeholders, including consumers, farmers, researchers, policymakers and representatives from the Mediterranean fruits processing industry.

Organised by EXCEL4MED Greek partners **NKUA**, **Smart Agro Hub (SAH)**, **ELGO-DIMITRA** and **SEVT**, in collaboration with **CIHEAM-IAMM**, the first Living Lab in Greece served as a pivotal platform for fostering collaboration and exploring sustainable innovations in the Mediterranean agri-food sector.

Participants

This Living Lab brought together **30 participants (stakeholders and consumers/citizens)** from a diverse range of sectors and expertise:

- **Farmers** shared valuable insights into agricultural practices and challenges.
- **Consumers/citizens** offered perspectives on product preferences and sustainability.

- **Retailers** provided input on market dynamics and customer demand.
- **Investors and processors** contributed expertise in funding and processing technologies.
- **Associations** presented collective viewpoints on industry trends.
- **Governmental organisations** shared insights into policies and regulations.
- **Local authorities** highlighted regional priorities and support mechanisms.

Activities and agenda

The day kicked off with a warm welcome from **Thomas Bartzanas (AUA)**, who set the tone for the event and outlined the objectives for the day. This was followed by a detailed presentation from our coordinator, **Associate Professor Vasilis Valdramidis (NKUA)**, who provided an overview of the **EXCEL4MED project**, explaining its goals, scope and potential impact. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions, engaging in an informative **Q&A session**.

After the introduction, each participant shared their background and expectations, fostering a collaborative atmosphere and helping everyone get to know each other. The morning continued with the presentation by **George Katsaros from ELGO-DIMITRA** and **Associate Professor Valdramidis**, who introduced new **green technologies** designed to improve **sustainability** in the **Mediterranean food supply chain**. These innovations sparked lively discussions on how they could be integrated into the project.

In the late morning, **Antigolena Folina (SAH)** introduced the **Living Lab concept**, explaining its key role in driving the project's objectives. This led into a series of interactive **Living Lab activities**, facilitated by **Georgios Kleftodimos** and **Aybike Bayraktar** from **CIHEAM-IAMM**. Participants used the **Q-methodology** to examine sustainability challenges and opportunities within Mediterranean food processing, engaging in vibrant discussions and brainstorming sessions.

The day concluded with a light lunch, offering a final opportunity for **networking** and **informal discussions**, where participants could continue to exchange ideas and explore potential collaborations (for further information, see Figure 13).

Methodologies applied

This Living Lab employed **Q-methodology**, a robust technique that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches to analyse subjective perspectives.

This method enabled participants to articulate their views on green technologies and sustainable practices, providing valuable ideas to guide project activities.

Main discussions and findings

Participants identified critical strategies for promoting healthier and eco-friendly processing methods within the Mediterranean fruit industry.

The discussions underscored the importance of aligning product innovation with growing consumer demand for sustainability. Additionally, stakeholders emphasised the need for stronger cross-sector partnerships to foster innovation and tackle common challenges.

Outcomes

Valuable insights were gathered from both stakeholders and consumers, which helped shape the direction of the project's activities.

The findings suggest that **smallholder farmers may not derive direct economic benefits** from innovative technologies. Therefore, mechanisms such as **cooperative-based production models** or **technology sharing centers** should be developed to ensure broader accessibility and impact. Moreover, the results highlight a **complex and multidimensional stakeholder structure** that goes beyond sectoral representation, emphasising the need to **strengthen participatory decision-making mechanisms** at the national level.

To enhance social acceptance of new technologies, participants recommended implementing **information campaigns, consumer education initiatives** and **joint learning environments** among value chain stakeholders. In Greece, a general trend was observed toward adopting innovative technologies aligned with energy and resource efficiency, consistent with the country's broader green transformation goals.

The session deepened the understanding of sustainability challenges and provided actionable recommendations for improving processing methods. Participants expressed **strong enthusiasm for future collaboration**, further reinforcing the Living Lab's role as a catalyst for innovation.

Dissemination and communication

- **Pre-event:** posts on the project social media platforms (Figure 15), an announcement on the project website (Figure 14) and direct invitations to potential participants (stakeholders, consumers/citizens).
- **Post-event:** posts on the project social media platforms (Figure 15), one article published in the project website (Figure 14) and one video summarising the event's outcomes available in EXCEL4MED YouTube channel (Figure 12), ensuring broad dissemination and visibility for the Living Lab's findings.

Figure 4. Pictures of the first Living Lab in Greece (4 July 2023)

2.3 Second EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece (27 September 2024)

Figure 5. Second Living Lab in Greece (27 September 2024)

General information

The second Greek Living Lab of the EXCEL4MED project was held on **27 September 2024**, at the Agricultural University of Athens.

The event brought together stakeholders from the Greek food and beverage sector to foster collaboration and co-create innovative solutions for sustainable Mediterranean food supply chains.

Organised by the **Federation of Hellenic Food Industries (SEVT)** in collaboration with **NKUA, ELGO-DIMITRA, SAH** and the **Region of Attica**, this Living Lab emphasised the importance of addressing sustainability challenges, particularly those related to pomegranates and citrus fruits, two high-value crops central to Mediterranean agriculture.

Participants

This second Living Lab brought together **22 stakeholders**, ensuring a comprehensive exchange of ideas and perspectives across a wide range of sectors. Notable organisations included **Papadopoulou**, the **Hellenic Association of Food Scientists & Technologists (Hel.A.F.S.T.- ΠΕΤΕΤ)**, **Heineken**, **Delta Foods**, **LAVDAS** and **NERA PIGON GRAMMOU**, among others.

The event saw participation from **experts, researchers, businesses** and **policymakers**, all united in a shared goal to **co-create solutions** for the pressing challenges within the

Mediterranean fruit supply chains. This diverse representation highlighted the importance of a broad **ecosystem** in addressing the complex issues facing food supply chains today.

To foster more focused discussions, participants were divided into smaller groups during **collaborative sessions**, enabling **effective brainstorming** and deeper engagement on key topics.

Activities and agenda

The event began with a **welcome address** by Dr. **Alkmini Gavriil (SEVT)**, who officially opened the session. This was followed by an **overview of the EXCEL4MED project**, presented by our coordinator, **Associate Professor Vasilis Valdramidis (NKUA)**, where he discussed the project's core objectives and its future aspirations to enhance Mediterranean food systems.

The morning continued with a series of technical presentations. **Dr. George Katsaros (ELGO-DIMITRA)** introduced **innovative green technologies**, focusing on their critical role in reducing food waste and driving **sustainability**. Next, **Artemis Chatzigeorgiou** from **DELTA FOODS SA** shared practical strategies and **best practices** for **product development**, emphasising the dual importance of meeting **consumer needs** while adhering to **environmental standards**. The final presentation by **Professor Georgios Kleftodimos (CIHEAM-IAMM)** provided an in-depth look at the **Business Model Canvas methodology**, explaining its relevance and application to fostering **business innovation** within the **agri-food sector**.

After these insightful presentations, participants engaged in a **collaborative workshop**, where they were divided into smaller groups to apply the **Business Model Canvas** to their own businesses. Each group worked on mapping key aspects such as **customer segments**, **cost structures**, **revenue streams** and **environmental impacts**.

Facilitators guided the discussions, ensuring that the outputs were **actionable** and in alignment with the project's broader goals. At the end of the session, each group presented its findings, providing an opportunity to compare approaches and inspire **cross-sector collaboration** (for further information, see Figure 13).

Methodologies applied

The Living Lab applied the **Triple Layered Business Model Canvas** as its central methodology, offering a structured framework to analyse and innovate across economic, environmental and social dimensions.

This methodology enabled participants to align their business strategies with sustainability goals, as well as facilitated collaboration between diverse stakeholders, ensuring outputs were both practical and innovative.

Main discussions and findings

This second Living Lab focused on driving innovation, sustainability, and value creation within the Mediterranean food sector. Key discussions and findings highlighted several important themes, such as:

- **Innovative business models:** participants explored various strategies to strengthen food supply chains, with an emphasis on reducing waste while enhancing adaptability and ensuring long-term resilience. The business structure of the companies participating in the Living Lab was generally similar, with most reporting that their key partners were suppliers and retailers, and that their main expenses related to raw materials, packaging, energy consumption, and transportation. Customer segments varied depending on the product, with some targeting children and others aimed exclusively at adults.
- **Green technologies:** advanced technologies were presented, showcasing their potential to minimise the environmental footprint of food processing and manufacturing. These innovations sparked discussions on how they could be applied to improve sustainability across the sector. While determining environmental impact is not the primary focus for many companies, some reported regularly producing environmental impact reports, recycling, and implementing energy reuse efforts.
- **Product development:** conversations revolved around practical methods for creating value-added food products that meet evolving consumer demands while adhering to sustainability principles. Some companies conduct taste tests in supermarkets and stores to better connect with their customers and often participate in food exhibitions.
- **Value chain efficiency:** stakeholders underscored the need for greater transparency, operational efficiency, and collaboration across the food value chain to achieve more sustainable outcomes. Nearly all companies actively use social media to engage with their customers, while TV advertising and participation in festivals or concerts were additional strategies to increase visibility and reach.

A recurring theme throughout the discussions was the recognition of the importance of **communicating environmental efforts to consumers**. However, many participants acknowledged gaps in their current strategies to effectively convey this message. There was a strong demand for eco-friendly and transparent food production practices, with several businesses emphasising their commitment to supporting local communities, including providing educational support for farmers and collaborating on initiatives that strengthen local development.

Stakeholders also pointed to **significant barriers to greater sustainability**, particularly the high costs of raw materials, energy, and transportation, which remain key challenges for the sector.

Outcomes

The **outcomes** of the session were significant, with participants developing new **business strategies** that seamlessly incorporated **sustainability** and **innovation**, specifically tailored to the Mediterranean food sector.

One of the most significant conclusions of this Living Lab is that, in general, companies in Greece do not focus on or **effectively communicate the environmental footprint** of their production processes. Addressing this gap will be a key priority in the development of new business models using innovative food processing technologies, ensuring that strategies explicitly incorporate and highlight environmental aspects.

The session also played a crucial role in **strengthening connections** among stakeholders, fostering a **shared commitment** to advancing and improving the **Mediterranean food systems**. This collaborative spirit laid the foundation for future joint efforts aimed at achieving long-term sustainability and innovation in the sector.

Dissemination and communication

- **Pre-event:** to build anticipation and ensure broad participation, a series of social media posts (Figure 15), an event announcement on the project website (Figure 14), and outreach materials, including a "Save the date" and invitations (Figure 11), were shared to promote the Living Lab and invite participants.
- **During the event:** live updates on the project's social media platforms (Figure 15) captured key moments, helping to maintain audience engagement throughout the event.
- **Post-event:** after the event, several activities were carried out to amplify its impact, including the publication of a detailed article on the EXCEL4MED website (Figure 14), multiple social media posts (Figure 15) and a press release distributed to relevant Greek media outlets (Figure 16). Additionally, a summary video was created and uploaded to the project's YouTube channel (Figure 12), ensuring that the event's outcomes reached both local and international audiences, further highlighting the impact of the discussions and findings.

Figure 6. Pictures from the 2nd Living Lab in Greece (27 September 2024)

2.4 Second EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta (21 November 2024)

Figure 7. Second Living Lab in Malta (21 November 2024)

General information

The 2nd Living Lab in Malta, hosted on **21 November 2024**, brought together diverse stakeholders at the **Corinthia St. George's Bay Hotel (Malta)** to explore innovative solutions for sustainable Mediterranean food systems.

Organised in collaboration with **MFA, MLSP, TMC** and **KM**, the event showcased EXCEL4MED's commitment to fostering collaboration and co-creation through interactive workshops and practical discussions, with a specific emphasis on aligning operations with sustainability goals.

Participants

The 2nd Living Lab in Malta brought together **57 participants** from a diverse range of organisations, such as Circular Economy Malta, Malta Innovation Hub, Bio Aqua Garden Ltd, representatives from the Ministry for the Environment, Energy and Public Cleanliness, the Food Safety Commission, Tanti and Mallia Quality Consultants, the Ministry of Gozo, and the National Veterinary Laboratory, among other organisations.

The wide array of participants facilitated a multi-faceted discussion, integrating viewpoints from industry, governance, consultancy, and academia to tackle the economic, environmental, and social challenges confronting Mediterranean food systems.

Activities and agenda

Josephine Schembri (MFA) opened the event with an overview of the EXCEL4MED project. Her introduction highlighted the project's focus on advancing green innovations and technological solutions for food waste valorisation in Mediterranean food supply chains, setting the stage for the day's discussions.

The **first presentation**, "Business Strategy for Fruit Products" was led by **Johan Zammit (MLSP/Malta Enterprise)** and **Aybike Bayraktar** from **CIHEAM-IAMM**, and it delved into strategies for using business approaches to bring high-quality fruit products to market, providing attendees with actionable insights on market dynamics and consumer engagement.

Following this, **Joseph P. Sammut**, Director of MediMalta Network and Malta Innovation Hub, introduced the concept of developing an innovation ecosystem in Mediterranean fruit supply chains. His presentation emphasised the role of EXCEL4MED in fostering sustainable collaboration among producers, processors, consumers and policymakers.

The event's collaborative spirit was further reinforced through **two workshop sessions**. The **first session**, "Local Food Production Case Studies", featured two concurrent workshops exploring the economic, environmental and social dimensions of local food production. Facilitators guided participants through case studies, encouraging a deep dive into practical examples of sustainable practices.

After a coffee break, the **second session**, "Strategy Development", focused on refining ideas from the first session. Participants worked on identifying resources, setting goals and developing practical steps forward. The facilitators ensured the discussions remained actionable, aligning outputs with the broader objectives of EXCEL4MED.

The day concluded with a final presentation and discussion, where participants shared ideas and outcomes from the workshops. This closing session summarised the collective efforts of the day, showcasing the value of collaboration and the innovative solutions proposed to enhance Mediterranean food systems (for further information, see Figure 13).

Methodologies applied

The **Triple Business Model Canvas** was the central tool for fostering collaboration and innovation in this second Living Lab in Malta, offering stakeholders a structured framework to address sustainability challenges in an integrated manner.

The **Economic Canvas** examined cost structures, revenue streams and market dynamics to identify actionable solutions. The **Governmental Canvas** explored governance frameworks, public-private partnerships and policy-related challenges; while the **Social Canvas** highlighted community impact, sustainability practices, and stakeholder collaboration.

Participants also discussed ESG frameworks and local adaptation of global sustainability standards, ensuring relevance to the Mediterranean context.

Main discussions and findings

The event highlighted a comprehensive and multidimensional approach to **sustainability**, focusing on the **economic, environmental** and **social** dimensions within the **agri-food sector**.

Participants discussed on **economic challenges and opportunities**, addressing financial and operational barriers such as high import costs, limited local production, and reliance on external supply chains. These factors were identified as critical obstacles to achieving greater **efficiency** and **resilience**.

Environmental sustainability emerged as a **central theme**, with stakeholders exploring strategies to minimise waste, enhance energy efficiency and reduce the ecological footprint of agri-food operations. Particular emphasis was placed on addressing the environmental degradation caused by waste generated from imported raw materials. Participants underscored the importance of adopting **waste valorisation strategies** and transitioning to **sustainable packaging** solutions to mitigate these impacts.

Social value and **community engagement** were also **key areas** of focus. Local producers shared their commitment to supporting communities through fair pricing, educational outreach programmes and collaborative partnerships. These initiatives were recognised as essential for fostering **social resilience** and **strengthening** the ties between producers and their communities.

Discussions also emphasised the need to align **product development** with evolving **consumer preferences**. Stakeholders agreed that healthier and more sustainable food options are essential to meeting consumer demand while advancing sustainability goals.

Outcomes

This second Living Lab in Malta uncovered significant opportunities to strengthen **local supply chains**, reduce **waste** and develop **value-added products**, such as jams and sauces made from by-products. These strategies aim to maximise resource utilisation while creating innovative, marketable solutions.

Participants highlighted the critical need for building **integrated ecosystems** that align the efforts and resources of diverse stakeholders. This approach fosters collaboration, streamlines processes and ensures that sustainability goals are addressed holistically across the value chain.

The findings from these discussions will play a pivotal role in shaping future strategies to minimise **environmental impact** while enhancing the **economic viability** of **local food systems**.

Dissemination and communication

- **Pre-event:** posts on the project’s social media platforms (Figure 15), an announcement of the event on the project website (Figure 14) and some digital materials (Figure 11) were shared to announce the Living Lab and invite participants.
- **During the event:** live updates via the project’s social media (Figure 15) highlighted key moments from the session.
- **Post-event:** a social media post (Figure 15), an article published on the EXCEL4MED website (Figure 14) and a summary video created and uploaded on the project’s YouTube channel (Figure 12).

Figure 8. Pictures from the 2nd Living Lab in Malta (21 November 2024)

Conclusions

Overall, the EXCEL4MED Living Labs showcased the value of participatory innovation and co-creation in tackling complex challenges, demonstrating the potential of collaborative and participatory approaches to addressing challenges in Mediterranean food supply chains. Across Greece and Malta, stakeholders from diverse sectors –ranging from industry leaders and researchers to policymakers, local producers and consumers– came together to co-create innovative solutions for sustainability, resilience and value creation in the Mediterranean agri-food sector.

A key outcome of these Living Labs is the alignment of economic, environmental and social priorities, ensuring that strategies not only address immediate challenges but also contribute to long-term sustainability. Each Living Lab highlighted the importance of fostering partnerships and building integrated ecosystems to enhance collaboration and streamline efforts. This approach has proven effective in promoting knowledge exchange and encouraging the adoption of best practices tailored to the unique needs of Mediterranean agriculture.

The methodologies applied, including the Q-methodology and the Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas, provided structured frameworks for innovation and problem-solving. These methodologies enabled participants to explore and develop strategies that aligned business goals with sustainability principles, from waste reduction and food waste valorisation to sustainable packaging and product development.

Discussions across the Living Labs highlighted several recurring themes. The need for greater transparency, operational efficiency and collaboration emerged as critical for strengthening Mediterranean food value chains. Stakeholders also recognised the challenges posed by high production costs, limited resources and evolving consumer demands, stressing the importance of adopting green technologies and innovative business models to address these barriers.

One consistent finding was the relevance of consumer engagement and education. Participants acknowledged the importance of communicating sustainability efforts effectively to build trust and encourage informed choices. Many stakeholders called for greater investment in awareness campaigns and educational programmes to bridge gaps between producers and consumers.

The Living Labs also underscored the need for policy support and financial incentives to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices. Stakeholders stressed that addressing systemic barriers such as the high costs of raw materials and energy would require coordinated efforts at the local and European levels.

Annexes

Figure 9. Roll-up banners for the EXCEL4MED Living Labs

Figure 10. Several materials distributed in the Living Labs

LIVING LABS

Join our Consumer Workshop

Excellence Hub in Green Technologies:
Introducing Innovation Ecosystems in the
Mediterranean Food Value Chain

5 May 2023 | 09:00

Malta Life Sciences Park, San Gwann

This project is funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research & Innovation of the European Union. Grant Agreement Number: 10101642

LIVING LABS

Join our Consumer Workshop

5 May 2023 | 09:00

Malta Life Sciences Park, San Gwann

3

days to go

EXCEL4MED

Excellence Hub in Green Technologies: Introducing Innovation Ecosystems in the Mediterranean Food Value Chain

LIVING LABS

ΠΡΟΣΚΛΗΣΗ

Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών
Ιερά Οδός 75, Βοτανικός
Αίθουσα Πολλαπλών Χρήσεων

27 Σεπτεμβρίου, 2024
10:00 - 14:00

Δηλώστε την συμμετοχή σας [εδώ](#)

Βρείτε το χάρτη [εδώ](#) ή σκανάρετε το QR code!

Funded by the European Union

EXCEL4MED

SAVE THE DATE

27 ΣΕΠΤΕΜΒΡΙΟΥ 2024
10:00 - 14:00

2nd LIVING LAB
ΓΕΩΠΟΝΙΚΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΑΘΗΝΩΝ
ΑΙΘΟΥΣΑ ΠΟΛΛΑΠΛΩΝ ΧΡΗΣΕΩΝ

Excellence Hub in Green Technologies: Introducing Innovation Ecosystems in the Mediterranean Food Value Chain

Funded by the European Union

SAVE THE DATE

21 NOV
Living Lab

#excel4med
EXCEL4MED

Funded by the European Union

Figure 11. Digital materials created for promoting the Living Labs (designs for the 1st Living Lab in Malta; designs for the 2nd Living Lab in Greece; QR code linked to an invitation for the 2nd Living Lab in Greece; and designs for the 2nd Living Lab in Malta)

EXCEL4MED: 1st Living Lab in Agricultural University of Athens, Greece

[Link to the video](#) (publication date: 13 July 2023)

2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece

[Link to the video](#) (publication date: 8 November 2024)

2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta

[Link to the video](#) (publication date: 20 January 2025)

Figure 12. Summary videos of the Living Labs (video of the 1st Living Lab in Greece; video of the 2nd Living Lab in Greece; and video of the 2nd Living Lab in Malta)

Day 1: 4 May 2023

Internal Project Partner Meeting		
09.00	Arrival at the venue	
09.15	Introduction and welcome team members	Joseph Sammut, MLSP
09.30	Preparation for the Living Lab 1 (T2.2 & 2.3) prepping of facilitators – 6 facilitators: – Aybike Bayraktar, CIHEAM – Georgios Klefodimos, CIHEAM – Joseph Sammut, MLSP – Diana Miceli, TMC – Josephine Schemberl, MFA – Daniel Schemberl, KM	CIHEAM & All Partners
12.00	Networking Lunch	
13.00	EXCEL4MED Living Lab Stakeholder Workshop (Innovation-Oriented Living Lab) (T2.3)	All Partners & Beneficiaries
	Introduction to the Workshop	Joseph Sammut, MLSP
	Overview of the EXCEL4MED Project	Diana Miceli, The Malta Chamber & George Psakis, UoM
	Proposed New Green Technologies	George Psakis, UoM
	EXCEL4MED Living Lab Stakeholder Workshop (to identify R&I needs for sustainable business & practices: 20-40 stakeholders)	CIHEAM co-facilitators: Aybike Bayraktar, CIHEAM Georgios Klefodimos, CIHEAM All Partners & Beneficiaries
14.15	Coffee break	
14.30	Continuation of EXCEL4MED Living Lab Stakeholder Workshop	CIHEAM co-facilitators: Aybike Bayraktar, CIHEAM Georgios Klefodimos, CIHEAM All Partners & Beneficiaries
16.30	Workshop Closure	Diana Miceli, The Malta Chamber
Internal Project Partner Meeting		
	Preparation for the Living Lab 2 (T6.3)	All Partners
18.30	Project Partner Dinner at Ta' Nenu - Each partner is to pay for their own meal.	

Day 2: 5 May 2023

Internal Project Partners		
08.45	Arrival at the venue	
09.00	Preparation for the Living Lab 2 (T6.3)	All Partners
09.30	Living Lab for Citizen Engagement (T2.1 & 6.3) Consumer acceptance to define the questions for the consumer survey	All Partners, Stakeholders & Citizens
	Introduction to the Workshop	Joseph Sammut, MLSP
	Overview of the EXCEL4MED Project & Living Lab Approach	Diana Miceli, The Malta Chamber & George Psakis, UoM
	Proposed New Green Technologies	George Psakis, UoM
	Workshop to understand the needs and products required by citizens	Facilitators: Diana Miceli, TMC George Psakis, UoM Aybike Bayraktar, CIHEAM Georgios Klefodimos, CIHEAM All Partners & Beneficiaries
10.45	Coffee break	
11.00	Continuation of Workshop to understand the needs and products required by citizens	Facilitators: Diana Miceli, TMC George Psakis, UoM Aybike Bayraktar, CIHEAM Georgios Klefodimos, CIHEAM All Partners & Beneficiaries
12.45	Workshop Closure	Diana Miceli, The Malta Chamber
13.00	Departure of Project Partners	

Excellence Hub in Green Technologies: Introducing Innovation Ecosystems in the Mediterranean Food Value Chain

LIVING LABS

ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑ - 4 ΙΟΥΛΙΟΥ 2023

Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών
Αίθουσα Πολλαπλών Χρήσεων (2^{ος} όροφος Κεντρικού κτιρίου)

09:00 – 09:30	Προσέλευση
09:30 – 09:40	Χαιρετισμοί Καθ. Β. Μπαρτζάνος (Αντιπρύτανης ΓΠΑ)
09:40 – 10:00	Επισκόπηση του έργου EXCEL4MED (Q & A) Αναπλ. Καθ. Β. Βαλδραμίδης (ΕΚΠΑ)
10:00 – 10:10	Σύντομη παρουσίαση των συμμετεχόντων Όλοι
10:10 – 10:30	Προτεινόμενες νέες πράσινες τεχνολογίες (Q & A) Δρ. Γ. Κατσαρός (ΕΛΓΟ) & Αναπλ. Καθ. Β. Βαλδραμίδης (ΕΚΠΑ)
10:30 – 10:45	Διάλειμμα για καφέ
10:45 – 11:15	Ενάντηση στις εγκαταστάσεις του ΓΠΑ
11:15 – 11:45	Παρουσίαση της νέας ΚΑΠ (Κοινή Αγροτική Πολιτική) (Q & A) Καθ. Κ. Τσιμπουκας (ΓΠΑ)
11:45 – 12:00	Εισαγωγή στο Living Lab (Q & A) κα Α. Φυλινα (SmartAgro Hub S.A.)
12:00 – 14:00	Living Lab (Q Methodology) Αναπλ. Καθ. Γ. Κλεφτοδύμιος & Δρ. Α. Bayraktar (CIHEAM-IAMM)

Ελαφρύ Γεύμα

Excellence Hub in Green Technologies: Introducing Innovation Ecosystems in the Mediterranean Food Value Chain

LIVING LABS

ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑ - 27 ΣΕΠΤΕΜΒΡΙΟΥ 2024

Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών
Αίθουσα Πολλαπλών Χρήσεων (2^{ος} όροφος Κεντρικού κτιρίου)

09:30 – 10:00	Προσέλευση
10:00 – 10:05	Χαιρετισμός Αλεξάνη Γαβριλά Υπεύθυνη Προγραμμάτων ΣΕΒΤ
10:05 – 10:25	Επισκόπηση του έργου EXCEL4MED (Q&A) Αναπλ. Καθ. Β. Βαλδραμίδης ΕΚΠΑ
10:25 – 10:45	Προτεινόμενες νέες πράσινες τεχνολογίες (Q&A) Δρ. Γ. Κατσαρός ΕΛΓΟ-ΔΗΜΗΤΡΑ & Αναπλ. Καθ. Β. Βαλδραμίδης ΕΚΠΑ
10:45 – 11:10	Καλές πρακτικές-στρατηγικές για την ανάπτυξη νέων προϊόντων (Q&A) Α. Χατζηγεωργίου R&D Director ΔΕΛΤΑ ΤΡΟΦΙΜΑ Α.Ε.
11:10 – 11:30	Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα στον αγροδιατροφικό τομέα (Q&A) Αναπλ. Καθ. Γ. Κλεφτοδύμιος CIHEAM-IAMM
11:30 – 11:45	Διάλειμμα για καφέ
11:45 – 14:00	Living Lab (new Business plan) Αναπλ. Καθ. Γ. Κλεφτοδύμιος CIHEAM-IAMM

Ελαφρύ Γεύμα

LIVING LAB FRUITful Future - AGENDA 21.11.2024			
Time	Agenda Item	Details	Speaker
08:30	Registrations & Networking/ Welcome Coffee		
09:00	Opening Remarks & Introduction to EXCEL4MED	Overview of an EU-funded project advancing green innovations and technological solutions for food waste valorization in the Mediterranean food supply chain.	Josephine Schembri, CO Market Regulation, Malta Food Agency
09:10	Business Strategy for Fruit Products	Using business strategies to bring high-quality fruit products to market.	Dr. Aybike Boyaktar, Ph.D. Researcher, Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier; Johan Zammit, Management and Innovation Consultant
09:20	Developing an Innovation Ecosystem in Mediterranean Fruit Supply Chains	Launching an Excellence Hub between Greece, Malta, and France to support sustainable collaboration across producers, processors, consumers, and policymakers.	Ing. Joseph P Sammut, Director, MedMalta Network and Malta Innovation Hub
09:30	Workshop Sessions Part 1: Local Food Production Case Studies	Two concurrent workshops exploring local food production, focusing on economic, environmental, and social impacts.	Workshop Facilitators
10:30	Coffee break		
10:45	Workshop Sessions Part 2: Strategy Development	Refining ideas from Part 1, focusing on resources, goals, and practical steps forward.	Workshop Facilitators
11:45	Final Presentation and Discussion	Summary of insights and outcomes from the workshops.	Workshop Facilitators
12:30	Lunch		

Figure 13. Agendas of the Living Labs (agenda of the 1st Living Lab in Malta; agenda of the 1st Living Lab in Greece; agenda of the 2nd Living Lab in Greece; and agenda of the 2nd Living Lab in Malta)

Stakeholders Living Lab in Malta

June 26, 2023

The first set of Living Labs for the EXCEL4MED project were recently held in Malta. The first Living Lab session involved engaging with stakeholders in discussions aimed at evaluating and promoting green technologies that can strengthen the Mediterranean agri-food supply chain. This session allowed for a fruitful exchange of ideas between stakeholders, with the aim of enhancing sustainability and promoting innovation in the food industry. Moreover, one of the primary research techniques employed in the living labs was the Q-methodology, a research technique that combines qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis. Q-methodology allows to identify and measure the subjective perspectives and attitudes of different stakeholders and users towards a particular product or service, which can then inform the design and development process.

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 26, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorization at the 38th EFFeST International Conference 2024
November 31, 2024
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- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at 'The Green Shift' webinar
December 28, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED seminar explores innovative applications of Pomegranate Seed Oil (PSO)
December 5, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 26 June 2023)

Consumers Living Lab in Malta

June 26, 2023

The second Living Lab session was an interactive workshop with consumers to capture their thoughts, ideas, and recommendations for the proposed green technologies. This session aimed to gather valuable insights into consumer perspectives and preferences related to sustainability in the food industry. Overall, the Living Labs were a success, providing valuable input from both stakeholders and consumers towards achieving the project's objectives. We are excited about organizing more Living Labs in the future and are committed to promoting sustainability and innovation in the Mediterranean food industry.

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 26, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorization at the 38th EFFeST International Conference 2024
November 31, 2024
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- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at 'The Green Shift' webinar
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- EXCEL4MED seminar explores innovative applications of Pomegranate Seed Oil (PSO)
December 5, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 26 June 2023)

First Greek Living Lab at the Agricultural University of Athens

August 3, 2023

The Agricultural University of Athens proudly hosted the first Greek Living Lab, a remarkable event that brought together a diverse community, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and representatives from the Mediterranean fruits processing industry. The Living Lab, held on 4th of July 2023, generated significant attention for its groundbreaking ideas and sustainable processing methods, aimed at revolutionizing the industry.

The Living Lab provided a unique platform for participants to collaborate, brainstorm, and exchange innovative ideas on processing methods that promote healthier and more environmentally-friendly products. Attendees were inspired by the collective dedication and enthusiasm displayed throughout the event, which bodes well for the future of the Mediterranean fruits processing industry.

The event would not have been possible without the invaluable contributions and active participation of project partners from Greece and France, stakeholders, and consumers.

The first Greek Living Lab marks a significant milestone in the journey towards a more sustainable Mediterranean fruits processing industry. With a focus on collaboration and pioneering ideas, the industry is well-poised to drive positive change in both the environment and the economy.

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 18, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorisation at the 38th EFSA International Conference 2024
December 31, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at "The Green Shift" webinar
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- EXCEL4MED seminar explores innovative applications of Pomegranate Seed Oil (PSO)
December 5, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED showcases sustainable innovation at ACAC 2024
November 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 3 August 2023)

2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece: Driving Innovation and Sustainability in the Mediterranean Food Supply Chains

October 18, 2024

On 27 September 2024, the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab was held at the Agricultural University of Athens, bringing together key stakeholders from the Greek food and beverage sector to foster collaboration and innovation. This event was organized by our Greek partners SEVT - Federation of Hellenic Food Industries, in collaboration with the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, ELGO-DIMITRA, Smart Agro Hub and the Region of Attica.

Living Labs are a hallmark of the EXCEL4MED project, designed to bring together industry experts, researchers, businesses and policymakers to co-create solutions for pressing challenges in Mediterranean food supply chains.

With a focus on pomegranate and citrus fruits, these labs serve as a dynamic platform for testing and refining innovative solutions in real-world settings, ensuring they address both immediate and long-term needs.

Key discussions at the 2nd Living Lab in Greece

Participants delved into a range of topics essential for the advancement of the Mediterranean agri-food sector:

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 18, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorisation at the 38th EFSA International Conference 2024
November 31, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at "The Green Shift" webinar
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- EXCEL4MED seminar explores innovative applications of Pomegranate Seed Oil (PSO)
November 5, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED showcases sustainable innovation at ACAC 2024
November 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 18 October 2024)

Join us at the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece!

September 12, 2024

Take part in the 2nd Living Lab of the EXCEL4MED project, organized by SEVT - Federation of Hellenic Food Industries, the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, ELGO-DIMITRA, the Region of Attica and Smart Agro Hub.

- When? Friday, 27 September 2024, from 10:00h to 14:00h
- Where? Agricultural University of Athens (Multipurpose Room, 2nd floor of the main building)

Check the programme of the event:

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 18, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorisation at the 38th EFSA International Conference 2024
December 31, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at "The Green Shift" webinar
December 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED seminar explores innovative applications of Pomegranate Seed Oil (PSO)
December 6, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED showcases sustainable innovation at ACAC 2024
November 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 12 September 2024)

Be part of the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta!

November 14, 2024

We would like you to take part in the upcoming 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta, hosted by the Malta Food Agency and the Malta Life Science Park (Malta Enterprise).

- When? Thursday, 21st November 2024, from 08:30h to 14:00h

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 18, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorisation at the 38th EFSA International Conference 2024
December 31, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at "The Green Shift" webinar
December 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 14 November 2024)

Highlights from the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta

December 9, 2024

On 21 November 2024, the Calistho St. George's Bay Hotel in Malta became the hub of innovation and collaboration for the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab. Organized in collaboration with Malta Food Agency, Malta Life Science Park (Malta Enterprise) and Eppanet@Malta, this event brought together diverse stakeholders to tackle pressing challenges in the Mediterranean food supply chains.

Fostering collaboration across sectors

Participants represented a broad spectrum of expertise, including industry leaders, policymakers, consultants and academics from organisations.

This diverse gathering created a vibrant space for multi-dimensional discussions, paving the way for actionable solutions in sustainability, food waste reduction and innovation.

Recent articles

- EXCEL4MED Newsletter No4
January 15, 2023
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED's research on citrus waste valorization at the 38th EFSA's International Conference 2024
December 31, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- EXCEL4MED shares circular and resilient innovations at "The Green SMRT" webinar
December 18, 2024
[READ MORE](#)
- Highlights from the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta
December 9, 2024
[READ MORE](#)

[Link to the article](#) (publication date: 9 December 2024)

Figure 14. Articles about the Living Labs published on the EXCEL4MED website (two articles on the 1st Living Lab in Malta; one article on the 1st Living Lab in Greece; two articles on the 2nd Living Lab in Greece; two articles on the 2nd Living Lab in Malta)

EXCEL4MED is at Malta Life Sciences Park.
Published by Thekli Bourtzinou
19 April 2023 · San Gwann, Malta

Living Labs (LLs) are on and rolling!
The Malta Chamber organizes the first LL in Malta which seeks to strengthen the Mediterranean agrifood supply chain.

This interactive workshop is being held to tap into your thoughts, ideas & recommendations for the proposed green technologies that may be suitable for your business, organisation or as a consumer.

5 May 2023
09:00
Malta Life Sciences Park, San Gwann

Learn more & register <https://lnkd.in/d/sPE-2B7>

#excel4med #horizonEU #livinglabs EU Science & Innovation #researchimpactEU #euinnovation

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 2 May 2023)

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 19 April 2023)

EXCEL4MED
12,218 followers
3yr · Edited · 🌐

🔥 We are excited to share some key insights from the recent EXCEL4MED Living Labs workshops, held in Malta on May 4-5, 2023!

Several project partners met to carry out the first set of Living Labs in Malta, one for stakeholders and one for consumers, to kickstart the EXCEL4MED journey with them!

CHEAM, EKTOIZQ, University of Malta, Malta Enterprise, The Malta Chamber, Koperattivi Malta, Malta Food Agency, Mgarr Farming

📍 EXCEL4MED Living Lab Stakeholder Workshop held on 4 May 2023:
 ✓ Stakeholders attended the first innovation-oriented living lab, T2.3, where they were informed about the EXCEL4MED Project and were asked to embark on the journey with the consortium.
 ✓ The proposed new Green Technologies were explained, and the stakeholders were enticed to learn more, benefit from increased nutrient extracts, and reduce waste of primary food products.
 ✓ Co-creation and co-design activities took place to identify and rank priorities using the Q Methodology as part of the meso-economic analysis of impacts and diffusion conditions of the innovation within industrial chains and territories (T2.2 and 2.3).

👥 EXCEL4MED Living Lab Consumer Workshop held on 5 May 2023:
 ✓ The first Living Lab for citizen engagement was held to kickstart the ecosystem-activity-process through co-creation activities for the initial stage of innovation.
 ✓ Consumers were informed about the EXCEL4MED Project and were asked to embark on the journey with the consortium.
 ✓ The proposed new Green Technologies were explained, along with their benefits in enjoying products with increased nutrient extracts.
 ✓ Activities also took place to identify and rank priorities using the Q Methodology as part of the meso-economic analysis of impacts and diffusion conditions of the innovation within industrial chains and territories (T2.2).

🙌 Thank you all for your participation!

📅 Stay tuned for our next Living Lab in Greece in one month!

#excel4med #livinglabs #HorizonEU European Research Executive Agency (REA)

excel4med

Just a few days left until our first Living Lab in Athens, and the team Anastasia Kapetanidou from SEVT, Antonios Fotini and Theodoros Kourou from Smart Agro Hub, Georgios Kichodimos and Aphike Bayraktar from CHEAM-IMM and George Katsaras from ELGO-DIMITRA ELGO-DIMITRA are finalizing the remaining details. Excited to come together and make great things happen!

👉 Sign up now to join us at <https://lilab.istgpa.gr/>!

👉 See you there!

#excel4med #livinglabs #horizonEU #researchimpactEU #EUInnovation @eu_science

Edited 41w

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 30 June 2023)

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 16 May 2023)

EXCEL4MED
Published by Thekiki Bouratzinou
5 July 2023 · 🌐

🔥 We are thrilled to announce the remarkable success of the first Greek Living Lab held at the **Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών – Agricultural University of Athens - Official!**

👥 This outstanding event brought together a diverse community, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and representatives from the Mediterranean fruits processing industry. Our participants had the opportunity to collaborate, brainstorm, and exchange groundbreaking ideas on sustainable processing methods for innovative and healthier products. It was truly inspiring to witness the collective dedication and enthusiasm towards creating a brighter and more sustainable future for Mediterranean fruits processing industry.

🙌 We would like to express our sincere appreciation to all the project partners from Greece and France, stakeholders and consumers for their invaluable contribution and active participation, as well as our esteemed project coordinator Vasilis Valdramidis from National & Kapodistrian University of Athens.

👉 A special round of applause goes to Smart Agro Hub, #SEVT and EKTOIZQ whose dedication and hard work brought this event to life.

👁️ Keep an eye out for the upcoming Living Labs in the coming months. Stay tuned for more updates!

#excel4med #livinglab EU Science & Innovation #researchimpactEU #euinnovation #HorizonEU

Video Home Live Reels Shows Explore Saved videos Following

George Katsaras from ELGO-DIMITRA took the lead and provided an introduction to the project along with the green technologies

🔥 Take a flashback to our first Living Lab in Athens! Enjoy a 45-second video featuring all the highlights! #excel4med #horizonEU #livinglab...

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👤 Talhada, Nextgenbioplast and 11 others · 53 views

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 13 July 2023)

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 5 July 2023)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
4mo · Edited · 🌐

📌 **SAVE THE DATE!**

Take part in our **2nd Living Lab in Greece** 🇬🇷!

📅 Friday, 27 September
🕒 10:00 - 14:00
📍 Agricultural University of Athens
🔗 Register at: <https://lnkd.in/d/PQhwGA>

The focus of this event will be on innovative business models, green technologies, and the perspectives of Food and Beverage businesses.

We will dive into how the value chain operates and explore strategies for developing new products in a sustainable and resilient way.

We are waiting for you!

#EXCEL4MED #HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

👍 33 7 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 13 September 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
3mo · Edited · 🌐

📌 Join us at the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece 🇬🇷 next Friday, 27 September, from 10:00h to 14:00h, at the Agricultural University of Athens!

We will discuss innovative business models, green technologies and value-added solutions for Mediterranean food supply chains.

Don't miss out! Get all the details of the event and register now via our website: <https://lnkd.in/d/2V69Sq>

#EXCEL4MED #HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

👍 33 1 comment · 9 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 20 September 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
3mo · Edited · 🌐

📌 Calling all Greek food & beverage businesses!

📌 Join us next Friday, 27 September, at the Agricultural University of Athens for the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab.

This event will bring together multiple stakeholders from the food and beverage sector, offering an interactive space to discuss:

- ✅ Innovative business models for sustainable food supply chains.
- ✅ Green and innovative technologies for the food industry.
- ✅ How the value chain operates.
- ✅ Practical solutions for the development of value-added food products in a sustainable and resilient way.

Do not miss this opportunity! Register here: <https://lnkd.in/d/2V69Sq>

#EXCEL4MED #HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

👍 11 3 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 25 September 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
3mo · Edited · 🌐

📌 The 2nd #EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece is happening now!

Researchers, companies and innovators in the food and beverage sector are coming together to create value-added products and reduce waste in Mediterranean food supply chains. 🇬🇷

A big thank you to all participants, especially to DELTA FOODS SA R&D Director, Artemi Chatzigeorgiou, for her contribution to this event, as well as the Agricultural University of Athens for hosting us.

📌 Stay tuned - more news about the Living Lab will come soon!

#HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

👍 ELENI ALEVRIYOU and 72 others 8 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 27 September 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
2mo · Edited ·

Want to know more about our 2nd **#EXCEL4MED** Living Lab in Greece?

Read our latest article and find out how we are driving innovation and reducing waste in the Mediterranean food supply chains!

<https://lnkd.in/dq59psEB>

#HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece: Driving Innovation and Sustainability in the Mediterranean...
excel4med.eu

Christina Simou and 32 others

5 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 18 October 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
2mo · Edited ·

Just released!

Take a look at the highlights of the 2nd **#EXCEL4MED** Living Lab in Greece, held recently at the **Agricultural University of Athens**, and see EXCEL4MED in action as we pave the way towards more ecological and resilient food systems in the Mediterranean region.

Watch here: https://lnkd.in/dm_rG7ki

#HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation

2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Greece
youtube.com

Christina Simou and 27 others

5 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 8 November 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
2mo · Edited ·

Save the date for the 2nd **EXCEL4MED** Living Lab in Malta!

Join us to explore innovative strategies and green technologies driving sustainability in the Mediterranean food supply chain.

This engaging event will bring together stakeholders from across the food and beverage sector, focusing on solutions for resilient, value-added food systems.

21 November 2024

08:30h – 14:00h

Corinthia St George's Bay Hotel, St. Julian's (Malta)

Register at: <https://lnkd.in/d6RkKbJ8Q>

Stay tuned – the full agenda will be shared soon!

#EXCEL4MED #HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation Malta Food Agency EIT Community RIS Hub Malta Malta Enterprise

Christina Simou and 22 others

1 comment · 11 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 14 November 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,216 followers
1mo · Edited ·

Only 2 days to go!

Get ready for the 2nd **#EXCEL4MED** Living Lab in Malta!

Join us this Thursday 21 November, from 08:30h to 14:00h, at Corinthia St. George's Bay Hotel (St. Julian's, Malta) for an inspiring day of collaboration, innovation and sustainability in the Mediterranean food supply chain.

Here is the agenda of the event. Do not forget to register!

<https://lnkd.in/eRwNNy6g>

#HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation Malta Food Agency Malta Enterprise EIT Community RIS Hub Malta

Christina Simou and 19 others

1 comment · 6 reposts

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 19 November 2024)

EXCEL4MED
1,220 followers
now · 🌐

📺 Our latest video is here!

Catch the highlights from the 2nd #EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta 🇲🇹, where researchers and food industry leaders came together to co-create strategies for a more sustainable and resilient Mediterranean food chains.

See how collaboration drives innovation!

▶ https://lnkd.in/dPAYui_z

#HorizonEU #ResearchImpactEU #EUInnovation #WIDERA European Research Executive Agency (REA) EU Science, Research and Innovation Malta Food Agency Malta Enterprise Koperattivi Malta

Key moments of the 2nd EXCEL4MED Living Lab in Malta
youtube.com

[Link to the post](#) (publication date: 20 January 2024)

Figure 15. Several posts about the four Living Labs shared through the EXCEL4MED social media platforms

[Link to the press release](#) (publication date: 5 December 2024)

[Link to the press release](#) (publication date: 5 December 2024)

[Link to the press release](#) (publication date: 6 December 2024)

[Link to the press release](#) (publication date: 6 December 2024)

1. EXCEL4MED : ΒΙΩΣΙΜΕΣ ΚΑΙ ΚΑΙΝΟΤΟΜΕΣ ΛΥΣΕΙΣ ΓΙΑ ΤΗΝ ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΑΚΗ...

Μέσο: INDUSTRY NEWSLETTER
 Ημ. Έκδοσης: . . .06/12/2024 Ημ. Αποδελτίωσης: . . .06/12/2024
 Σελίδα: 12

Innews AE - Αποδελτίωση Τύπου - <http://www.innews.gr>

|| ΟΛΟΚΛΗΡΩΘΗΚΕ ΤΟ 2ο LIVING LAB

EXCEL4MED: ΒΙΩΣΙΜΕΣ ΚΑΙ ΚΑΙΝΟΤΟΜΕΣ ΛΥΣΕΙΣ ΓΙΑ ΤΗΝ ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΑΚΗ ΑΛΥΣΙΔΑ ΤΡΟΦΙΜΩΝ

Στο Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών φιλοξενήθηκε το 2ο Living Lab του έργου EXCEL4MED, ενός χρηματοδοτούμενου από την ΕΕ έργου στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon Europe, που στοχεύει στην ενίσχυση της εφοδιαστικής αλυσίδας φρούτων στην περιοχή της Μεσογείου μέσω της καινοτομίας, της βιωσιμότητας και της συνεργασίας. Το Living Lab συγκέντρωσε βασικούς παράγοντες από τον ελληνικό κλάδο τροφίμων και ποτών, για να συνδημιουργήσουν και να δοκιμάσουν νέες ιδέες, με σκοπό να αντιμετωπιστούν κρίσιμες προκλήσεις, όπως η σπατάλη τροφίμων και ο περιβαλλοντικός της αντίκτυπος.

Η εκδήλωση συνδιοργανώθηκε από τον **ΣΕΒΤ - Σύνδεσμο Ελληνικών Βιομηχανικών Τροφίμων** και την Περιφέρεια Αττικής, σε συνεργασία με το Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών, τον ΕΛΓΟ-ΔΗΜΗΤΡΑ και το Smart Agro Hub.

No link available (publication date: 6 December 2024)

1. EXCEL4MED : ΣΥΝΔΗΜΙΟΥΡΓΙΑ ΒΙΩΣΙΜΩΝ ΛΥΣΕΩΝ ΓΙΑ ΤΗ ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΑΚΗ...

Μέσο: FOOD REPORTER

Ημ. Έκδοσης: . . .06/12/2024 Ημ. Αποδελτίωσης: . . .06/12/2024

Σελίδα: 6

Innews AE - Αποδελτίωση Τύπου - <http://www.innews.gr>

**Excel4med:
Συνδημιουργία
βιώσιμων λύσεων
για τη μεσογειακή
αλυσίδα τροφίμων**

Στο Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών πραγματοποιήθηκε το 2ο Living Lab του ευρωπαϊκού έργου Excel4med, που χρηματοδοτείται από το πρόγραμμα Horizon Europe. Στόχος του έργου είναι η ενδoκoυση της αλυσίδας εφοδoιασμού φρούτων στη Μεσόγειο μέσω καινοτόμων και βιώσιμων πρακτικών. Το Living Lab συγκέντρωσε εκπροσώπους από τη βιομηχανία τροφίμων, ακαδημαϊκούς, ερευνητές και φορείς χάραξης πολιτικής, προωθώντας τη συνεργασία για την αντιμετώπιση προκλήσεων όπως η σπατάλη τροφίμων και η περιβαλλοντική επιβάρυνση.

Στη συνδιοργάνωση συμμετείχαν ο **Σύνδεσμος Ελληνικών Βιομηχανικών Τροφίμων (ΣΕΒΤ)**, η Περιφέρεια Αττικής, το ΕΚΠΑ, ο ΕΛΓΟ-Δήμητρα και το Smart Agro Hub. Ο Αναπληρωτής Καθηγητής Βασίλης Βαλδραμίδης παρουσίασε το έργο Excel4med. Ειδικοί όπως ο Δρ. Πάργος Κατσαρός από τον ΕΛΓΟ-Δήμητρα, ανέδειξαν καινοτόμες πράσινες τεχνολογίες, ενώ η Άρτεμις Χατζηγεωργίου της Delta Foods SA παρουσίασε βιώσιμες στρατηγικές ανάπτυξης προϊόντων.

Μέρος της εκδήλωσης αποτέλεσε η διαδραστική συνεδρία του Αναπληρωτή Καθηγητή Γιώργου Κλεφτοδήμου από το CIHEAM-IAMM. Οι συμμετέχοντες εργάστηκαν σε ομάδες για τον σχεδιασμό βιώσιμων επιχειρηματικών μοντέλων. Τα νέα σχέδια που προέκυψαν επικεντρώνονται στη μείωση της σπατάλης, την αύξηση της αποδοτικότητας και την προώθηση προϊόντων προστιθέμενης αξίας.

No link available (publication date: 6 December 2024)

1. EXCEL4MED : ΒΙΩΣΙΜΕΣ ΛΥΣΕΙΣ ΣΤΗ ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΟ

Μέσο: RETAIL TODAY

Ημ. Έκδοσης: . . .06/12/2024 Ημ. Αποδελτίωσης: . . .07/12/2024

Σελίδα: 12

Innews AE - Αποδελτίωση Τύπου - <http://www.innews.gr>

EXCEL4MED: ΒΙΩΣΙΜΕΣ ΛΥΣΕΙΣ ΣΤΗ ΜΕΣΟΓΕΙΟ

Στο **Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών** φιλοξενήθηκε το 2ο Living Lab του έργου **EXCEL4MED**, ενός χρηματοδοτούμενου από την Ε.Ε. έργου στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon Europe, που στοχεύει στην ενίσχυση της εφοδιαστικής αλυσίδας φρούτων στην περιοχή της Μεσογείου μέσω της καινοτομίας, της βιωσιμότητας και της συνεργασίας. Το Living Lab συγκέντρωσε βασικούς παράγοντες από τον ελληνικό κλάδο τροφίμων και ποτών, για να συνδημιουργήσουν και να δοκιμάσουν νέες ιδέες, με σκοπό να αντιμετωπιστούν κρίσιμες προκλήσεις, όπως η σπατάλη τροφίμων και ο περιβαλλοντικός της αντίκτυπος. Τα Living Labs είναι δυναμικά περιβάλλοντα σχεδιασμένα για την προώθηση της ανοιχτής καινοτομίας μέσω της συνεργασίας μεταξύ επιχειρήσεων, ερευνητών και άλλων σημαντικών φορέων. Σε αυτά τα πραγματικά περιβάλλοντα, οι καινοτομίες δοκιμάζονται, βελτιώνονται και εξελίσσονται μέσω ανατροφοδότησης, επιτρέποντας πρακτικές προόδους που ανταποκρίνονται στις πολυπλοκότητες των μεσογειακών συστημάτων τροφίμων. Η εκδήλωση συνδιοργανώθηκε από τον **ΣΕΒΤ - Σύνδεσμο Ελληνικών Βιομηχανιών Τροφίμων** και την **Περιφέρεια Αττικής**, σε συνεργασία με το **Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών**, τον **ΕΛΓΟ-ΔΗΜΗΤΡΑ** και το **Smart Agro Hub**. Περισσότερα στο CSRnews.gr.

άλλων σημαντικών φορέων. Σε αυτά τα πραγματικά περιβάλλοντα, οι καινοτομίες δοκιμάζονται, βελτιώνονται και εξελίσσονται μέσω ανατροφοδότησης, επιτρέποντας πρακτικές προόδους που ανταποκρίνονται στις πολυπλοκότητες των μεσογειακών συστημάτων τροφίμων. Η εκδήλωση συνδιοργανώθηκε από τον **ΣΕΒΤ - Σύνδεσμο Ελληνικών Βιομηχανιών Τροφίμων** και την **Περιφέρεια Αττικής**, σε συνεργασία με το **Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών**, τον **ΕΛΓΟ-ΔΗΜΗΤΡΑ** και το **Smart Agro Hub**. Περισσότερα στο CSRnews.gr.

No link available (publication date: 6 December 2024)

1. EXCEL4MED : ΠΡΑΓΜΑΤΟΠΟΙΗΘΗΚΕ

Μέσο: CSR WEEK

Ημ. Έκδοσης: . . .10/12/2024 Ημ. Αποδελτίωσης: . . .11/12/2024

Σελίδα: 9

Innews AE - Αποδελτίωση Τύπου - <http://www.innews.gr>

Στο **Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών**

EXCEL4MED: Πραγματοποιήθηκε το 2ο Living Lab

Στο **Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών** φιλοξενήθηκε το **2ο Living Lab** του έργου **EXCEL4MED**, ενός χρηματοδοτούμενου από την Ε.Ε. έργου, στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος **Horizon Europe**, που στοχεύει στην ενίσχυση της εφοδιαστικής αλυσίδας φρούτων στην περιοχή της Μεσογείου μέσω της καινοτομίας, της βιωσιμότητας και της συνεργασίας. Το Living Lab συγκέντρωσε βασικούς παράγοντες από τον ελληνικό κλάδο τροφίμων και ποτών, για να συνδημιουργήσουν και να δοκιμάσουν νέες ιδέες, με σκοπό να αντιμετωπιστούν κρίσιμες προκλήσεις, όπως η σπατάλη τροφίμων και ο περιβαλλοντικός της αντίκτυπος. Η εκδήλωση συνδιοργανώθηκε από τον **ΣΕΒΤ - Σύνδεσμο Ελληνικών Βιομηχανιών Τροφίμων** και την **Περιφέρεια Αττικής**, σε συνεργασία με το **Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών**, τον **ΕΛΓΟ-Δήμητρα** και το **Smart Agro Hub**. Περισσότερα στο CSRnews.gr.

No link available (publication date: 10 December 2024)

Figure 16. Publication of the press release on the 2nd Living Lab in Greece in different Greek media (businessnews.gr; csrnews.gr; selfservice.gr; industry-news.gr; Industry newsletter; FOODReporter; Retail Today; and CRS Week)